

EDUCATIONAL VALUES IN TRADITIONAL IDIOM OF MELAYU JAMBI

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Abstract

This research is based on the needs of the Malayu Jambi community in communicating culture. The problems of this research were; (1) what educational values are there in the idiom of Malayu Jambi, and (2) how the implementation in daily life. The purposes of this study were; (1) to describe educational values in the traditional idiom of Jambi Malay, and (2) to describe the way in using it on the Jambi Malay community. The data of this study were in forms of spoken data and written data. Ethnography method with extralingual equivalent was used to analyze the data. The result of this study revealed that the educational values is a useful trait or attitude to mature humans in getting perfect life.

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1. Introduction

Education values can be put and used in the language. Jamaris [2008] states that the value of education can be seen as follows; (1) the value of trusting education of God, 2) the value of intelligence and skill education, which are derived from the goal of improvement, and (3) the value of moral education, derived from the educational objectives of enhancing the character and strengthen personality.

According to Hymes (1979), in assessing the use of language in the community, we have to consider about the context of the situation so the language does not stand alone as a study of grammar, personality, social structure, religion and so on. He also states that in assessing ethnography of speaking, we need to comprehend some of aspects such as ways of speaking, speech community, and situation.

Jambi Malay language is used as a tool of communication in spoken or written language. The application of the language is applied in all of the society, social level, customs, and the local culture [Dahlan, 1999]. The disclosure of the phenomenon of life in social culture of Malayu Jambi can be seen through the use of language in the traditional idiom. The traditional idiom is a part of folklore. Folk is the people who have the characteristic of cultural users different with other community, and lore is tradition of folk which is inherited through examples accompanied by behaviour [Danandjadja, 2008].

The idiom of Seloko Malayu Jambi has description of word choice, language style. Style in the idiom of traditional Jambi Malay is the words of praise which rise the effects of the wealth of language and culture of a person, diction and style of the clause arise based on the intuitive thinking of language and the experience and intellectual property of the speaker [Burridge, 1991].

Look at the following phrase:

Rumah nan berpagar adat, laman nan besapu undang

Home has custom, home has rules

2. Research Method

The most common method of collecting data used in cultural domains is observation-participation [Ibrahim, 2004]. This method was used in collecting data. Moreover, observation and taking a note method were also used in collecting the data. Both of these techniques are used when the researcher as an outsider during the communication even though the presence of researchers is not far from the communication situation. However, the relationship between ethnographer researchers and the speech community needs to be maintained in emotional connection and it is not too biased in interpreting behavior because researcher has the same culture.

The base of cultural meaning of the life society is formed from the relationship of the language symbols. The language of life in communication to create a culture, then the value of culture itself that will ultimately determine the communication system in the form of language as what is appropriate for it [Djadjaudarma, 2002; Mahsum, 2005].

3. Finding and Discussion

First, the value of religious education teaches the consciousness and the existence of god as the creator of nature. It confesses to the essence and power of god with piety and faith only to him. Religious values show the relationship among human beings as a creature created by god with a god as a contrarian, for example, believe in destiny, as illustrated in the following phrase.

Adat besendi sarak: sarak besendi kitabullah

Moreover, expressing gratitude can be interpreted as a sign of gratitude of what Allah has given for us, as an example:

Kito bedo'a pado ilahi: Semoga kito dilindungi; Sehat badan murah rezeki

In addition, submissiveness means surrender fully to Allah control, and accept what has been given because everything has been arranged and has become his will. As one of the creatures of god, man should have a resignation.

Bukan tambak sembarang tambak: tambak dari datuk temenggung: Bukan kendak sembarang kendak: Kendak dari ibu mengandung.

Furthermore, the value of ethical education is good or bad attitude and actions of a person in social life. Ethics serve the human concept to perform actions or behavior toward others in life. Ethics is a knowledge related to the determination of the deeds of humans do to be good or bad. In other word, ethics is the role of human behavior which generated by human reason. The value of ethical education includes speech and politeness. It is illustrated as follows.

Kalo tidak karano dibulan: Tildaklah aek pasang pagi: Kalolah tidak karano tuan: tidaklah kami sampai kemari.

Besides, politeness relates to the actions or behavior of a person who can place himself in front of others. Politeness is an attitude that every human must have.

Kok maagih agih sampai; Kok bejalan sampe ke bateh; jalan berembek nan ditempuh

Further, the value of social education made the concept for every human behavior as a member of society such as: affection, loyalty, and exemplary illustrated in the following expression.

Senang hati; kecil telapak tangan niru kami tadahkan; begitu nian suko hati kami menerimo kedatangan nenek mamak.... tarimolah siring pnang; tando kato aakan bejawab; rundingkan dimasak... gemertu bunyi dendang, gendang jenang ilir ke jambi; sirih kerukup, pinangnyo mumbang; iko nan ado pado kami, tando mato kasih sayang.

In short, loyalty can be interpreted as obedience and loyal to the boss or leader. It is a human's attitude about how humans interact very carefully without bring into conflict. Thus, an attitude of loyalty needs to be instilled in ourself from an early age.

Duo Belas gayung ke jambi; putik nanas dalam kebun; idak belas memandang kami; siang kepanas malam berembun.

Exemplary is imitative which refers to customary rules, for example:

Kalo bejalan buatlah sebagai tongkat; kelam menjadi suluh; tidur jadikan bantal; mudah-mudahan Allah besamo kito, Aminn.

Second, the value of moral education related to the manners or morality of actions or behavior of a person in social life and based on the virtue with the act of loving and caring each other and other living creatures, for example; patience, keeping promises, willing to sacrifice, humble, and not despair.

Patience is a commendable behavior and every human must has it. Human must accept everything that has been given.

Samo-samolah kito berdoa supayo ado batang melintang paga; yang mengepung dan unan nak mengait.

Additionally, the attitude of keeping promises is a picture of humans who have noble character. If someone promised, he have to keep it. Promise is an act dealing with the moral deeds of human.

Anak gagak duo-duo; anak elang di kayu tinggi; anak bapak nan surang iko; Tunggang ilalang berani mati; tak menepati janji.

Willing to sacrifice is including a commendable attitude. Willing to sacrifice does not mean seeking the attention of others or praise.

Bukan awak menerawang semak; Semak menerawang batang kemir; bukan awak membuang sema; semak membuang badan diri.

Humble attitude can be interpreted not boast, not arrogant, but always inferior and succumb.

Kalo tuan mengambil bambu; bambu dibukit menjadi sangkar; kalo idak kareno ibu, idaklahkami menjadi pintar

Not easily discouraged is a commendable attitude. Trusting that God gives the trials of life to his people based on the abilities possessed of the human.

Dari jupun hendak ke jupun: urang jupun sudah menanti; biak rintangan apapun; menuntut ilmu idak berenti.

Firmness is the ability of a person in terms of looking or believing something.

Sebenarnya malu nian kami datang ke siko; raso idak tetepi mato pedang; raso idak tertendang matohari; idak alur makan patut; idak layak bakal judu; anak pungguk ingin di bulan; atilah samo bekato; matolah samo besetan; mamulu-malu kami diusap; pedih-pedih hati ditekan.

4. Conclusion

The value of education is a useful attitude in an attempt to mature humans into a perfect life. This attitude in the traditional idiom of Malayu Jambi is found in form of religious values, such as believe in destiny, offer a sense of gratitude, and be surrender. In ethical values is found in form of attitude of speech and politeness. In social values is found that the affection, loyalty, and exemplary. In moral values can be found that patience, keeping promises, willing to sacrifice humble, not easily discouraged, not criticizing or interfering of others, strong determination, and helping others. All of these attitudes are contained in the traditional idiom of Malayu Jambi.

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